

**GLOBALIZED MUTIFICATION AND SHARED TRAUMA:
A TRANSCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF FORSTER'S *A
PASSAGE TO INDIA***

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Abstract

Today, almost one third part of world has experienced about the colonialism and rights are being suppressed and they are mutified against the power dynamics .So the backdrop has been set against the dehumanization of human in a colonial period. The aims and objective of this research are to explore how subjugated people are mutified and made powerless in A passage to India. To analyze shared trauma of the individuals as presented in the novel. To determine how characters resist against colonial powers and how this resistance is limitless. This research uses a qualitative approach because there is no need of numerical data. The primary source of this study is *A Passage to India* and the secondary sources include all the articles, quotes and papers used to support this study. This research incorporates the transcultural trauma theory focusing on the perspectives of Cathy Caruth which describe about the effect of dehumanization on their psyche and the effect of colonialism lead to the trauma. This research analyses the data using research question way. The research describe about the suffering and struggles of colonized people for their rights and existence. This research challenges the patriarchal norms and power dynamics that tried to oppressed and marginalize people with resilience and strong determination.

Keywords: *Dehumanization, Exploitation, Mutification, Powerlessness, Resilience, Resistance, Subjugation, Trauma.*

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1. Introduction

A Passage to India (1924) by E. M. Forster, set against the backdrop of colonialism, explores cultural difference and human relationships. This novel portrays the tension between the Indian population and British colonizers. It describes the divide and the misunderstandings of the people. It tried to focus on the human relationships and their lives through characters. The novel portrayed symbolically, including the Mosque, the Caves and the Temple. It tried to expose the Injustice, identity and meanings with respect to cultural differences. The selected fiction describes an Indian doctor who became a friend of Moore and Adela. Then he was accused with an assault of assaulting Adela, and Aziz had to face several challenges and hardships to prove him innocent. In this way novel tried to explore the different aspects of the dehumanization of people under colonial rule. It especially deals with imperialism and social inequality, which are able to raise several questions. This novel is rich with textured narrative and complex characters and reveals the prejudice, misunderstandings, and cultural dissonance that underpin colonial relationships. It also depicts the true situation of power dynamics and loss of true identity, hardships, and the complexity of colonized people who are oppressed by the colonizers. And especially this novel focuses especially on the effects of colonialism on common people.

1.1. Statement of the problem

Today, almost one-third of the world has experienced colonialism, and rights are being suppressed, and they are mutinous against the power dynamics. So the backdrop has been set against the dehumanization of humankind during the colonial period. It describes the oppression of rights, and the people suffer from identity crises, displacement, and it has a great impact on their psyches. Through the characters of his novels, all these things are being portrayed by Forster. It describes the exploitation and suppression of rights, and these things are present in the globalized era. My theory of transcultural trauma is going to describe the culture and race relations, misunderstanding and oppression of the British on the Indian colonized people. They have to face several challenges that make their life a disaster and have a bad impact on their psyches. It describes boundaries that reshape identities with the hybridity of culture, and especially the oppression of identity over colonized people. It describes the environment of alienation and oppression due to colonizers and colonial rule.

1.2. Research Objectives

The aims and objectives of this research are;

- To explore how subjugated people are mutified and made powerless in *A Passage to India*.
- To analyze the shared trauma of the individuals as presented in the novel.

- To determine how characters resist against colonial powers and how this resistance is limitless.

1.3. Research Questions

1. How subjugated people are muted and made powerless in *A Passage to India*?
2. How are shared traumas of the individuals presented in this novel?
3. How do characters resist against colonial powers, and how is the resistance limited?

1.4. Research Significance

Colonialism is an exploitation of people and their resources, especially related to the native language, culture and politics. *A Passage to India* by Forster describes the experience of colonized people in India, their sufferings and struggles to revive their culture and identity. Previous research has explained angles of colonialism, race, and oppression on Indian people. Furthermore, these studies have explored how colonized people resist against colonial powers and what makes their lives miserable. It further explores racial divisions, showing the impossibility of friendship between colonizer and colonized people. It describes boundaries, identity, hybrid culture and especially the identity that was influenced by power dynamics. I have explore this according to the lens of transcultural trauma that how colonized people have to face colonialism and all the events under post-colonial pressure, and due to oppression and violation of rights, people have a bad impact on their psyche and are being mutated under power dynamics. Postcolonial encounter has a great impact on individual, cultural and historical wounds. It further explores the environment of mistrust and alienation within the society. It helps future researchers to read the novel and explore different lenses due to his setback.

2. Literature Review

Morse (2011) explored the connections between national traditions and the transnational flow of literary forms because he was very sensitive. In Fannegan's wake, washerwomen set a great example of friendship. Forster describes friendship and culture, but is also influenced by economic and political forces. The description was great. The friendship has been disrupted due to colonialism, in which the rights of people are suppressed. They would not be able to take their life according to their will and greatly noise no Importance. They are dehumanized, and they have to live their life according to colonial rule under a patriarchal and authoritative structure. Forster's concept of Intimacy had great importance, which describes have to face obstacles in for better and to create their own Identity; they have to struggle hard for the betterment as in *Howard End* the efforts of sister to adopt with noble intentions lead to their ultimate failure and their social or political condition to make their Identity, people have to suffer hard and their struggle bore fruit and they empowerment comes. Some people have to face the placement with in

with in country or out of the country because they have gone away from their traditions and culture, which are Important for them (Morse, 2011).

According to Lan, (2013) Forster completely focuses on the societal circumstances and treats the environment. He fully kept an eye on Victorian optimism in the Edwardian period. He remains unchanged throughout his life. He always comes forward for the marginalized antiques and toward their Independence. He is a great fighter as well as a great writer. He never wants to combine two different things. He connects the Imperialism with the history and personal relations. He uses liberal humanism as a tool to protect the humanity. He describes the personal relations; British rule in India is not safe for the colonized people. They have to suffer the colonial rule and the stress upon the people with colonial mindsets. Al-Saidi (2018) states that the loss of India to the Britishers is a great downfall because people would be able to colonize about their rights. The middle class began to realize their Importance and about their rights. They began to resist the colonial rule. The rule started with penetration, which was not proper for the British Empire. They come to know that the British Empire is just an illusion and not practically fit in reality. Because Hindus and Muslims bring trouble to their rule (Lan, 2013; Al-Saidi, 2018).

Tavassoli (2014) European nations ruled over almost every country and have a great Impact of culture on politics and economics. But everything revolves around their Eurocentric opinion that European literature covers all the traditions of feminism the social dominance. Colonialism covers the exploitation and dehumanization of women throughout world. Women face violence and dehumanization in this patriarchal society. *A passage to India* describes the relationship between India as colonized and the British as colonizers. They have great difference between these related to culture, tradition, race and language. Through the character portrayed about the fact and reality. The British women are considered superior, and Indian women are inferior. Forster's satires on post-colonialism and Western culture and tradition. He depicts English women as self-righteous, resistant and always seen as Inferior to the native people. He demonstrates and its expansion and challenges the assumptions that women's lives and histories around the world are the same. The women have to suffer the bad standards of society which gave no rights and their struggle for Identity and for the empowerment and women's experience related to colonialism (Tavassoli, 2014).

Bharali (2012) investigates the national Identity, which is important for every person. He also interrogated about the grandmother describe about the fever explore about the reality and unreality and valid and invalid national Identity, which was made with the traditional constructions, such as about the nation, their nationality and about the nationalism which was depicted through their manners, language and the traditions which they follow. Nationality is based on three types of borders: Identity about the people, political conditions and societal values and the decisions taken by the political parties and

governance and their decision, which were approved by the army make the safety of a country is acceptable and respectable. The Nationality also found with the different cultures and races, lived a shared their experiences, there bonding creates nationality, they leave behind their cultural difference and only faces the national Identifiable shadow lines describe about that the where nation in a single flag, others are used to depict their nationality and create and make them together and show unity it encompassing cultures and traditions together (Bharali, 2012).

Bartiza & Zrizi (2022) find out about the post-colonial theory that is multidisciplinary and its basis forms a number of domains and describes discipline and mainly focusing on women's rights, the study of the mind, philosophy, societal values, and about anthropology. It also describes mainly in literature, which explains the locations and the people that are colonized, and all their history and present through literature, colonizers' language and literature as a tool in order to show their authority and power over the native people. Then natives began to understand the Importance of their own language, literature, culture, and tradition. They used language as a tool of resistance against this colonial rule. The Eurocentric culture and language represent the English culture, leaving all other cultures behind in the globalized era. Ghimire (2012) states that Post-colonialism describes native people as inferior and it seeks to make them superior and to civilize them. But the only purpose behind all these things is getting profit from the colonized land, which is known as the golden sparrow. But Native people resist against colonialism and struggle hard for the development of ecology, social justice, and feminism socialism to protect their own rights, Liberalism and their national identity (Bartiza & Zrizi, 2022).

Madhavi & Rao (2023) state that Tony Morrison's *Beloved* (1987) is a great and complex work that highlights the slavery of African people under colonialism. Morrison used postcolonial theory to expose the colonizer's mind and thinking, and they tried to shape their own Ideology. The rights of native people have been marginalized. They suppress, and they portrayed in their literature as the African people are uncivilized and they came there to civilize them, but they make them Inferior and become superior while doing. The marginalization of African culture and traditions to get their Identity suppressed, and they have to face the challenges and harsh experiences. Morrison describes the Importance of their Identity and resists the legacy of colonialism. He describes the African culture and traditions that are suppressed. The women are considered to give birth to more slaves. The author challenges post-colonialism and inspires the coming generations through their works. He drew the attention of the world to the struggle of African people. So, the understanding of their problems and they would be able to get social justice and be rid of the complex and painful history of colonialism. He describes the Importance of the culture and language of native people (Madhavi & Rao, 2023).

Daghamin (2019) analyzes the racial conflict and tension faced by the colonized people. He loves humanity, morality, believes in love, peace, sympathy and mutual understanding of people. India is divided based on religious culture and language, which leads to racial discrimination. They repeat their hospitality, improve their social understanding and are responsible for the many misunderstandings of English people and social Indians. The Indian people are divided with respect to power, status, class, race class and especially on a religious basis. So, the Britishers considered themselves superior, and the local and native people considered inferior. It is about the downward and marginalized condition of the people, which leads to the oppression of their Identity, rights, their experiences lead to mental breakdown. Forster pays more importance to the conditions and experiences and their struggle for Identity with class distinction, both are absurd and Inapplicable. The novel describes how the native people, language, tradition, their societal manners and especially their Identity have become marginalized. It further explores the universal love understanding and describes the Importance of pure love, which takes people together (Daghami, 2019).

Shahparan (2023) explores that the cultural conflicts in Forster's works from post-colonial perspective describe that there is a great difference between English people and Indian natives. The British considered them superior and called the native people Inferior and treated them as slaves and suppressed their Identity and treated them as Inequality, and their lives became a great hell. In the early about, they both considered themselves right for each other. But later, the truth is revealed, and the native people become against the colonizer because they understand the Inequality. Later, things became clear; they were not at all because native people would be able to understand their Identity. At the end, they tried to make things normal, but now the possibility was equal to zero. Their belief of to become superior has changed their attitude towards native people. The colonizer views them and realizes the importance of their culture, which makes them powerful against all these circumstances. They would be able to understand the reality of their existence, and they fought and struggled hard for the existence of their rights and for even their own presence. So, they would be able to regain their Identity, cultural tradition, which shapes their Identity, (Shahparan, 2023).

3. Theoretical Framework

Transcultural theory was described by Cathy Caruth which is about the traumatic experiences of people across different cultures, times, and individuals. It explains the repetition of dreams of flashbacks, which is used to reveal the trauma through the disruption of time and memory. Trauma is not easily described through words or images, so it needs a language to capture the depth. So literature became a mouthpiece for the people who are facing trauma in colonialism. This theory overlaps with the concepts of Homi K. Babha's friend's content and adverts, which explores the after effects of

colonization on the identity of the people, fragmentation, and displacement through colonialism. These theories focus on the unspoken suffering and historical injustices of the people who are suppressed through generations and their rights are violated, and they are not considered equal.

This theory overlaps with the psychoanalytic theory, which describes the traumatic returns and the symptoms in those people who have experienced war and all these things disrupts language and subjectivity, and the personality becomes fragmented, so it provides space. These focus on the rights of people and especially the rights of women who are living in a male-dominant society and have a true struggle for a better life and for identity, and especially for their existence, with behavioral silence creating a transcultural echo of trauma. These theories explore angles about chromatic effects of individuals which have a great impact on their psyche, and they're unprocessed experience, which disrupts the linear flow of time and reveals their silence about events such as war, colonization, and displacement. It further explains the culture and national trauma, which is not limited to, and the research of *A Passage to India* with the transcultural trauma lens. This research describes the dehumanization of people.

Cathy Caruth's transcultural trauma theory (1996) describes the traumatic experiences of people across different cultures, times, and individuals. It explains the repetition of dreams of flashbacks, which is used to reveal the trauma through the disruption of time and memory. Trauma is not easily described through words or images, so it needs a language to capture the depth. So literature became a mouthpiece for the people who are facing trauma in colonialism. Transcultural trauma theory overlaps with postcolonial theory, psychoanalytic theory, and family and gender theories. This theory overlaps with the concepts of Homi K. Bhabha's friend's content and adverts, which explores the after effects of colonization on the identity of the people, fragmentation, and displacement through colonialism. These theories focus on the unspoken suffering and historical injustices of the people who are suppressed through generations and their rights are violated, and they are not considered equal. This theory overlaps with the psychoanalytic theory, which describes the traumatic returns and the symptoms in those people who have experienced war, and all these things disrupts language and subjectivity, and the personality becomes fragmented, so it provides space. These focus on the rights of people and especially the rights of women who are living in a male-dominant society and have a true struggle for a better life and for identity, and especially for their existence, with behavioral silence creating a transcultural echo of trauma.

The trauma studies lead to the presentation of bad experience in belatedness. According to Cathy Caruth, trauma does not appear physically but leads to mental breakdown. It becomes difficult for a person to express traumatic experiences, and it is difficult to heal, so the traumatized person needs storytelling to heal, which is possible

through literature. Literature is also a form of testimony; a novel is in the form of testimony to express traumatic experiences in a fictional subject. Freedom is in the form of psychological expression, so different writers describe different traumas in different ways. Trauma is a central issue for Cathy Caruth. She described her experience as a parting trauma, silence, and survival, which creates a secondary role in thinking and trauma. She claims about grappling with the implications of surviving and about overwhelming events, and about the departure of the battery. With the Battery on Traumatic experience about Trauma and Creativity challenges common accounts of trauma theory, which might need theorization of trauma, through which we might understand the Ruskin and Huron's perspectives.

Trauma is used to describe a story that explores identity, memory, and selfhood. PTSD and child trauma are most popular in the writings of trauma. Its plot is flattened, distorted, instructive, and insistent upon morality and ethics. This is used as a connection to describe further about trauma through the departure of history and ourselves, Taylor & Francis (2021). It further explores the responsibility for life and describes about three issues which were forced by people related to their rights identity, and dehumanization for existence. It questions social life and societal norms, and it describes the database of trauma with an extremely vivid and rich literary picture. It describes mental distress and pain due to inner experience, which badly affects the life experiences of people.

4. Analysis and Discussion

This research aims to describe the exploration that how subjugated people are marginalized and made powerless in *A Passage to India*. It helps to analyze the shared trauma of the individuals as presented in the novel and determine how characters resist against colonial powers and how this resistance is limitless. It further questions how subjugated people mutified and made powerless in *A Passage to India*. And how shared traumas of the individuals presented in this novel. It questioned how characters resist against colonial powers and how the resistance is limitless. It is analyzed with Cathy Caruth's transcultural trauma theory, the experiences of people across different cultures, times and individuals. Trauma is not defined through one person; it crosses cultural and historical boundaries to express experiences of people with war, colonization and migration, which have a great effect on the lives of the people.

The first question of this research discussed how subjugated people are mutified and made powerless in *A Passage to India*. The novel clearly depicts the character of Adela which accused doctor Aziz and the trials and difficulties which has to be faced by the doctor Aziz. This subjugation and mutification of the people is evident in the novel. "The very wood seems made of mud, the inhabitants of mud moving. So abased, so monotonous is everything that meets the eye" (Forster, 1924, p. 3). It describes about the landscape, which shows the dehumanization and diminished of the native people. It describes the

colonized people are invisible and voiceless, and having no rights. The Britishers considered Indians as nothing more than slaves and masses. The Indians are considered uncivilized and are denied their basic rights. They have no rights to education, employment and other basic rights, and they were ruled by colonizers. "It matters so little to the majority of living beings what the minority, which calls itself human, desires or decides. Most of the inhabitants don't mind about the governed" (Forster, 1924, pp. 139-140). Then Forster criticizes the ruling elite who consider themselves humans and keep dominating the colonized people. Through this lens, it is exposed that people have no power of decision, and they were marginalized and muted by the rulers through the political and social circumstances.

The second question of this research discussed how trauma of the individuals is presented in this novel. The trauma that was faced by individuals and society has a great impact on their psyche, like Aziz like who accuses and tries, which is considered trauma. As Forster states that "What does unhappiness matter when we are all unhappy together? She remarked that it meant. To her, as to the three men" (Forster, 1924, p. 98). These emotions show the colonial fate collectively show the colonial and colonized deep and unspoken context, and their difference between racial and social groups and these are through isolation, alienation and futility are common between them. It further describes the psychological imprisonment and the connection and cultural tension between the colonists and the universal unhappiness that was faced through the oppressive colonial atmosphere. All these emotions lead to trauma and disgrace of the colonized people, Englishman us except Mr. Fielding, he thought; but how shall I see him again? If he entered this room, the disgrace of it would kill me"(Forster, 1924, p. 126). It further explores the mistrust and misunderstanding of the colonial subject and reveals the system that became the reason for insult, shame and fear and led the British gaze. Aziz's trauma is misunderstood by an English person, which prevents a genuine connection. It leads to feelings of inferiority and the colonizer's ignorance, which causes distance and pain for both colonizers and colonized people.

The description of the atmosphere makes the trauma clearer and is greatly presented through the novel, which is meaningful and chaotic. "The sound had sputtered after her when she escaped, and was going on still like a river that gradually floods the plain. Only Mrs. Moore could drive it back to its source and seal the broken reservoir. Evil was loose; she could even hear it entering the lives of others" (Forster, 1924, pp. 222-223). It further explores the Marber caves' collective trauma. The echo of the Marabar caves shows meaninglessness that was depicted through the characters of Adela and Mrs. Moore, which shows the whole community. The evil spreads in the lives of people, sense of fear and shard misunderstanding that destroys the trust and stability of society. The echo becomes haunting for both races, and the cave incident depicts it clearly. The trauma that

leads to disconnection and fragmentation, and individuals consider their life has no meanings, which lead to questions about their existence. All these things lead to existentialism.

The third research question discussed how characters resist against colonial powers and how this resistance occurs. It further explores challenges faced by colonizers and the resistance that they show in colonial rule. "Oh Lord, oh Lord! When I live here-he kicked the gravel- and you live therefore, not minutes from cow is right ever so far away from here. Then how did you come to be passing the Cow Hospital on the way to me" (Forster, 1924, p.78). Through this quote, we understand the colonized people's resistance when Aziz reveals Adela's truth through the sharp observation and understanding of the situation. Aziz has shown through questioning authority and the hypocrisy of Adela's lie. Through this, the colonizers understand that the colonized people which a, able to reveal dishonesty and absurdity in the colonial rule, is a great example of resistance. It keeps the British and Indians apart from each other, which leads to physical rejection and rebellion against the colonizers and the authoritative rule.

The resistance became important against the colonizers and the British rule. It leads to their revival of identity and culture in true aspects. "Kindness, Kindness, and more Kindness-yes, that he might supply, but what that really all the queer nation needed. Did it not also demand an occasional intoxication of the blood" (Forster, 1924, p. 143)." Fielding questions about the benevolence raises moral complacency. The colonized people need passion, self-determination and vitality. This is a form of resistance against the colonizers and needs to anticipate the revolutionary energy to show resistance and rebellion and lead to self-awakening. This resistance is not efficient, but it has been beneficial in colonial power. Their resistance is important in physical, allied and mental aspects, which pushes back the presence of colonizers. "By May, a barrier of fire would have fallen across India and the adjoining sea, and she would have to remain perched up in the Himalayas waiting for the world to get cooler" (Forster, 1924, p. 160). The barrier of fire represents the physical climate and social tension that had built up in India. And the summer in India becomes an image of colonialism and an image of the rising colonial system, which is uncontrollable, elemental and inevitable. And the nature mirrors the colonial subject resistance is unstoppable and vast. So, it became difficult for the British to maintain their rule.

This becomes personal resistance against this colonial rule and the search for independence. "If it were not for his black face, we would almost allow him to join our club. The approval of your compatriots no longer interests me, I have become anti-British, and ought to have done so sooner; it would have saved me numerous misfortunes" (Forster, 1924, p. 281). Aziz's rejection of the British of India to get independence. It is a revolt against colonial ideology and their culture. They fought for their rights and against the

racial barriers that exposed the inequality and the racial discrimination. It led to the latest act of liberation, and it became an important aspect of colonial rule.

The novel clearly shows resistance against the colonial rule through the characters. It was sweet to have his sons with him at his moment, and to know they were affectionate and brave. He pointed out that the “Englishmen were state guests, so they must not be poisoned, and received, as always, gentle yet enthusiastic assent to his words”(Forster, 1924, p. 330). The novel depicts native interaction with the British guests which portraying the dignified and strategic resistance. It shows loyalty with autonomy and moral superiority. This shows collective national pride and limited cultural vitality in resistance against colonial rule.

This research analyzes *A passage to India* from the perspective of Cathy Caruth in the theory of transcultural trauma, which is used to discuss the trauma that was faced by people in different experiences across different cultures, times and individuals. So, the novel describes the trauma which is faced by Indian people and their resistance against all these circumstances of colonization and migration and the dehumanization of people. The novel *A passage to India* has been discussed in different perspectives of colonialism, imperialism and about the concepts of subaltern people. This research describes about the depiction of trauma data explored further questions these describe about the problematizing of narrative in the late 20th century, which investigate about reality through ideological implications involved in the creation of structure of making and meaning. They show the consequences of abuse and genocide of culture.

5. Conclusion

To conclude, this research describes the tension between the Indian population and British colonizers. It describes the divide and the misunderstandings of the people. It tried to focus on the human relationships and their lives through characters. The novel portrayed symbolically, including the Mosque, the Caves and the Temple. It tried to expose the Injustice, identity and meanings with respect to cultural differences. This research aims to describe the exploration that how subjugated people are marginalized and made powerless in *A Passage to India*. It helps to analyze the shared trauma of the individuals as presented in the novel and determine how characters resist against colonial powers and how this resistance is limitless. It further questions how subjugated people mutified and made powerless in *A Passage to India*. And how shared traumas of the individuals presented in this novel. It questioned how characters resist against colonial powers and how the resistance is limitless.

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